

Alleviating methods of the irritant effects of Capsaicin on humans and investigation of the efficiency of its other effects : antioxidant and insecticide.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Background

Methods

Chilli peppers from the genus *Capsicum* are cultivated in more than 64 countries with China, Mexico, Turkey, Indonesia and India producing the vast majority of the world chilli peppers production. In 2013, India accounted for 40% of this production. According to the French Institut national de la recherche agronomique (INRA) there are more than 1,200 varieties of Chilli peppers. These owe their difference to their origin and their concentration in capsaicin.

Capsaicin is the active component of chilli peppers causing the sensation of burning in humans and other mammals when it comes into contact with tissue, more commonly the oral mucosa. When eaten, the compound produces pungency (spiciness or "heat"). This chemical irritant which belongs to alkaloids is believed to have protection purposes in the plants producing it, against animals and fungi.

Christian Friedrich Bucholz first extracted Capsaicin compound in 1816 and it was then first synthesized in 1930 by Ernst Spath and Stephen F. Darling. Numerous of its effects and benefits have been discovered and investigated since. Capsaicin was tested and used as a defense ingredient causing breathing difficulties (personal defense sprays or riot control in the United States); as an equestrian doping substance to reduce pain in horses; as a poison in some extremely rare cases; as a treatment against psoriasis; as a weight loss strategy complement; as a euphoric substance in very rare reported cases; as perfume component (Bertrand Duchaufour); as a topical analgesic in dermal patches or cream form; as a pharmaceutical drug to reduce the symptoms of peripheral neuropathy; and as an insecticide. It was also reported that Capsaicin may reduce the incidence of some severe diseases due to its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and anti-cancer properties.

In this research, the effects on humans when consumed in food is investigated. Alleviating methods through these food aliments of the irritant effects of Capsaicin on humans is assessed and further investigations of the efficiency of its other predominant effects: antioxidant and insecticide, are carried out.

Results and Conclusions

Among the 10 components we found that dairy products such as milk and butter which contains casein work up to 70% better than any other food in alleviating the pungency effects of Capsaicin. This is caused by the casein molecules (of which milk is 80% contained) taking the place of Capsaicin on the TRPV1 receptors. The TRPV1 receptors are located within taste receptors in the taste buds of papillae. When Capsaicin is exposed to the receptors, it leads to the activation of sensory neurons responsible for the sensation of burning. The neuronal signal is very dependent on calcium and sodium ions, the higher their concentration, the weaker the signal gets. Desensitization is achieved when casein which contains calcium ions binds on the TRPV1. The dislodged capsaicin, a fat-soluble element, is then dissolved in milk (which is high in lipids) or other fatty substances. Other common aliments such as tuna also contain casein (in sodium phosphocaseinate form) which is also working but less efficiently than dairy aliments (with calcium phosphocaseinate).

In addition, it was reported that components with a sweet taste (sugar, banana) deliver a nervous message to the brain that is seem to have a stronger response than the capsaicin one, which as a consequence made some individuals feel less the effects. The T1R2/T1R3 sweet taste receptors responses overtake the TRPV1 response. Starch-based foods, such as bread or rice, absorb capsaicin better than dairy products, but they do not displace capsaicin away from the TRPV1 receptors as efficiently as milk does with casein. Therefore bread added to a dairy product would give alleviating effect up to 90% greater than other components tested. Water and water-rich aliments such as tomato had no effects or aggravated the burning sensation. Alcohol or hot liquids were reported to associate with the pungency effect and the sensorial response for the Capsaicin appeared stronger to the individuals tested. Time remained the best way to reduce the capsaicin concentration and therefore the effect on humans.

We also have demonstrated the effect of antioxidant against food oxidation (fruits: apple and banana). Capsaicin delayed and alleviated the oxidation of the outside surface in contact with oxygen reacting with polyphenoloxidase. However it did not show a significant increase in the antioxidant effect comparing to other similar elements like citric acid. Total Antioxidant Capacity (TAC) of chilli pepper is measured to be 709 $\mu\text{mol per 5 ml}$. Capsaicin appears to act as barrier against free radicals. Free-radical theory of aging states that aging mechanisms are due to cells accumulating free radical damage over time.

The insecticide effect (general term which includes any lethal effect on Arthropod animals) was tested on spiders (against control group). In order to testify a real efficiency of the capsaicin, its concentration needs to reach high Scoville concentration. We investigated further than our laboratory experiment showing its practical uses in Thua Thiên-Huê farms.

The main contribution of this research is the identification and demonstration of an optimized means of alleviating the effects of Capsaicin on humans by combining Casein with starch-based aliments. This research study also highlighted and consolidated the state-of-the-art and the antioxidant and insecticide effects which are rarely investigated for Capsaicin. The main limitation of this study is the sample size and the diversity of the testers: only 12 French individuals took part in this study.

Keywords: Capsaicin, Alleviating pungency, Casein, Antioxidant, Insecticide, Chilli peppers effects

Capsaicin Extraction and Chilli Pepper samples assessment with Scoville Scale

First, a capsaicin homogenate is produced for three different chilli pepper types (green, yellow and habanero) following a grinding procedure with 20ml of Ethanol for each homogenate. Capsaicin is very soluble in Ethanol. This is in order to assess and measure their relative concentration in capsaicin and therefore their potential burning sensation strength (Scoville scale).

Scoville scale is used a reference for the measurement of the pungency (spiciness, burning sensation strength or "heat") due to Capsaicin in Scoville Heat Units (SHU). The scale was developed in 1912 by Wilbur Scoville.

Vacuum/Suction filtration apparatus is used to separate solids (left (chilli pepper) in the homogenate from the capsaicin-rich liquid. Capsaicin is then extracted with a fractional distillation setup for each of the chilli pepper types. Each capsaicin-rich liquid is heated to a temperature of 80°C which is carefully monitored. Ethanol evaporates from the liquid (with a 75°C boiling temperature). The vapor is then immediately channeled into a condenser into an Erlenmeyer flask. Capsaicin which has a higher boiling temperature of 210°C remains in the distilling round-bottom flask. The distillation process ends as soon as a slight coloration is observed in the Erlenmeyer flask.

Thin-layer chromatography with silica gel plate under UV light is used to measure the concentration of Capsaicin in each of the three Capsaicin distilled liquids and compared against a solution with known-concentration of Capsaicin derived from the Baume St Bernard (Merck laboratory) which contains Oléorésine de capsicum (0.25g/100g) an oil with 2% Capsaicin.

Alleviating Experiment

10 aliments (peanut butter, sugar, banana, bread, olive oil, tomato, lemon juice, milk, water and sweet potato) are tested on 12 individuals (aged 15 to 18 years old, including 7 females and 5 males) for three different levels of concentration of capsaicin determined from the Extraction (from three different chilli peppers: green: 250-2,500 Scoville, yellow: 5,000-10,000 Scoville and habanero: 100,000 – 335,000 Scoville)

The aliments were selected from the existing scientific literature (through systematic review), press articles as well as preliminary tests which were carried out to assess their subjective suitability for alleviation of the pungency. The increase in pungency or in the burning sensation due to these aliments is also investigated.

The 12 testers used a standardized scale from 1 to 10 with brief descriptions for each number which was then converted to the Scoville scale (from 0-100 to 16,000,000 (pure Capsaicin)). The scale was used to assess the reduction in pungency for each aliment and each chilli pepper time. Recovery time of one to seven days was given between each test, to minimize inaccuracies.

The testing subjects are being closely observed and interrogated on their irritation and sensation of burning of their oral mucosa during the entire course of the experiment. Mathematical and statistical modelling are then applied to the data collected from the experiment.

Antioxidant and Insecticide Experiments

The antioxidant effect is tested by measuring the reduction-oxidation on series of slices of apple and banana with a capsaicin-rich coating against control samples of the same fruits. The concentration of Polyphenol oxidase and melanine are used a measure of the efficacy of capsaicin as an antioxidant for fruit. The same concepts would apply to redox reactions in humans.

Two groups of Araneae from the spider species have been gathered from collected, preselected and prescreened Aranea from natural habitat, based on their observed health conditions. One group is put in a flask with Capsaicin-rich water droplets and vapor for 6 hours; another control group is put in the same flask in identical conditions without any Capsaicin for also 6 hours. Both groups are closely observed to look for signs of weakness or death.